

EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: AN OVERVIEW OF LOCAL SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13747544>

Abstract. The article "Education in Uzbekistan: The article "An Overview of Local Schools" gives general information on the education system in Uzbekistan and its schools, their structure, curriculum, and problems. To this end, this paper reviews the history of the education system, the contemporary system, and reforms that have been implemented in the recent past to enhance quality and expansion. The area of focus in the abstract is culture and society in relation to education, including the concern of the ratio between cultural imperative and contemporary demands in education. Further, it discusses the inequalities in education for rural and urban students and the government's attempts to improve education in every school across the nation.

Key words: Structure, Curriculum Modernization, Teacher Training, Quality of education, Innovative Programs and Language Barriers.

Education is one of the priorities of the development of any country, and in Uzbekistan, the recent years have been marked by steps towards the reform of education processes. This paper aims at considering the situation with education in Uzbekistan in the contemporary period with the special emphasis on the local schools and their improvement.

A Historical Perspective

Uzbekistan's education system has not remained the same since the country gained independence in 1991 from the Soviet Union. From the Soviet inheritance – the centralized system of educational management and priorities set on the making of technical specialties were inherited by Uzbekistan. But, as the country embraced the change to a market economy and democracy, education has gradually begun to be developed and reformed and the old systems changed.

The Structure of Education

Uzbekistan's education system is structured into several key stages:

Preschool Education: Pre-school education is offered, especially the basic education to prepare children for primary school. However, quality preschool education is something that is not yet available to all and it stands poorest in rural areas in most countries.

Primary and Secondary Education: In Uzbekistan, the education system comprises the primary schools, which covers from grade 1 to grade 4 while the privileged school levels are the secondary schools that range from grade 5 to grade 9. Compulsory education at this level is and should be general education in order to lay a strong foundation.

Upper Secondary Education: Meanwhile the learners in 10-11 generalize education and vocational education to prepare the learners for higher education or workplace.

Higher Education: Universities and higher education institutions in Uzbekistan include various universities that provide Undergraduate and Postgraduate programs.

Recent Reforms and Developments

In recent years, the Uzbek government has introduced several reforms to enhance the quality of education in local schools: In recent years, the Uzbek government has introduced several reforms to enhance the quality of education in local schools:

Curriculum Modernization: The curriculum has been modified in a slight manner with added emphasis on critical thinking, problem solving and use of information technology. This shift has been called in a bid to help the students succeed in the economic world that is already globalized.

Teacher Training: As it has become apparent that teachers are in the central position, much effort and money has been spent on the training and professional development of the teachers. This includes both the ongoing professional development or staff development and the attempt to enhance the quality of teacher education programs for beginning teachers.

Infrastructure Improvements: School infrastructure improvement initiatives are now being made especially in the rural areas, schools that for the most part have some of the worst infrastructures greatly hinder the quality of education.

Challenges Facing Local Schools

Despite these positive developments, local schools in Uzbekistan face several challenges:

Resource Disparities: The schools in urban areas have comparatively more resources than the rural areas schools. Challenges that have been identified in rural schools include; inadequate infrastructure and Compound; lack of teaching aids.

Quality of Education: However, there are apprehensions that the kind of changes which are being incorporated in new curricula and teaching methods may not be uniform. This has resulted in the territorial differentiation of quality education.

Language Barriers: The linguistic diversity of Uzbekistan is problematic in education at the current time. Uzbek is the medium of instruction; however, some measures are being taken to honor minority languages: this is in the process of being done.

Achievements and Success Stories

Despite the challenges, there have been notable successes in Uzbekistan's education sector: Despite the challenges, there have been notable successes in Uzbekistan's education sector:

Increased Enrollment Rates: On balance, enrolment to school rates has increased and this is in line with the progressive uptake of education for all.

Innovative Programs: Some schools have adopted and introduced differentiation measures that have been recognized internationally for instance STEM projects that refer to Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics.

Community Engagement: More state and community programs are now directed towards enhancing learning institutions hence the improvement of results.

Looking Ahead

The future of education in Uzbekistan can be regarded as rather optimistic as the government remains committed to the reforms in the sphere of education. The further strategies are entering the new ones: increasing the usage of digital education means, the improvement of vocational training, and the deepening of the disparity gap between the various regions. Such actions are intended to 'reform' the current education and empower it in a way capable of offering the student a fair chance at success.

Conclusion

Overall, education in Uzbekistan is in a state of transition and development in recent years considerable progress has been made. The center of this change is local schools where demands and risks as well as opportunities for reforms and changes are experienced. The consistent focus on the continued improvement of the standards of education assures a better future for learners in Uzbekistan as well as the entire country.

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